

Language Theses and Dissertation Landscapes: An Analysis of Research Analyses

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Abstract

Content analysis of language research is one of the very widely researched topics worldwide. However, in the Philippine context, few studies and systematic reviews on the content analysis of language theses and dissertations are published. The current study examined the features of 25 studies that looked at the content of language theses and dissertations published from 2016 to 2021. Thematic focus, study design, data analysis methodologies, and research outcomes were all investigated. The findings show that research trends, research parts, rhetorical structures, and linguistic structures are the most commonly discussed topics. Content analysis is the most widely used methodology and data analysis approach. It is worth noting that only one of the reviewed studies produced a research output. Recommended topics and areas for future language research are offered.

Keywords: Content Analysis, Systematic Review, Language Research, Theses, Dissertations, Research Features

Introduction

There has been a growing interest in academic studies analyzing theses and dissertations. Researchers of different fields of specialization have centered on examining the specific topics or subjects in their domain. Specifically, theses and dissertations have been the subject of countless research due to their volume of knowledge (Tullay, 2019).

Research has been carried out in a variety of disciplines, including psychology and related fields, information science, educational technology, natural and applied sciences, mathematics, education, and many other fields to evaluate the different features and scope of the studies (Panolong, 2018; Tullay, 2019).

Giritlioglu (2014), for example, conducted a content study of hospitality PhD dissertation topics in Turkey. Through a content analysis of 263 dissertations, Piotrowski

and Guyette (2014) investigated the selection of business ethics topics for dissertation study. Temel et al. (2016), on the other hand, examined the various facets of MA and PhD research categorized under sports from 2010 to 2014, while Yetkiner et al. (2019) investigated the PhD curriculum evaluation studies in Turkey based on various variables.

Erdogan (2015) also looked into the research trends in problem-based learning (PBL) studies from 2002 to 2013. Feeney (2014) looked at the use of newspapers in research. Horton and Hawkins (2010) examined the content of dissertations in two doctorate degrees in business.

Furthermore, Sampson & Gresham (2017) investigated gender research in school administration leadership, while Miville et al. (2017) conducted content analyses on empirical studies on psychological literature dealing on gender roles among Latina/o respondents, concentrating on content areas, sample properties, and methods.

In the field of language, several studies from language curricula, printed works, and citations, among other things, have already been analyzed by researchers. These analyses focused on various parts and features of the studies.

Motha (2009) concentrated on second-language pedagogy in the United States. It looked at about 500 doctoral dissertations that centered on issues, such as linguistic rule, and second/foreign language pragmatics, among others. Online corpora and reference tools, conversation analysis, and the reconceptualization of private speech were also among the other main topics covered.

Lin and Cheng (2010) also analyzed 493 abstracts from theses published within 2003 to 2007 to find research patterns in TESOL programs (master's level) in the Taiwanese context. It was revealed that most of the research took place in the secondary or undergraduate levels. Key study subjects listed are language skills, instructional methods, resources and programs, and computer-assisted language learning.

In the same line, Solak (2014) used 189 published publications to determine trends in foreign language education in the Turkish context. The year of publication, authors, the language of the study, journal index, topic of the paper, research design, data collection tools, sample, sample size, and data analysis method were checked. Concept analysis, teaching, and learning were the most frequently studied topics; the highest quantity of articles was written in 2013 with the majority using the English language, the authors were mostly Turkish, the quantitative method was used more often as research design, sample group was mostly undergraduates, and 31-100 samples was the ideal size.

Before this, Karadag (2010) had previously clustered research methodologies and statistical approaches made use in 211 unpublished PhD papers written between 2003 and 2007. Experimental design, survey, correlational study, and case study techniques were utilized, and descriptive statistics, t-tests, and ANOVAs were seen to be the most commonly used statistical procedures.

In the European setting, Tuma and PISOVA (2013) evaluated 59 PhD dissertations

in foreign language pedagogies in Czech higher education institutions to determine the key study subjects and then equated them to global education. The results revealed that management of the teaching/learning process was the most popular topic, trailed by foreign language acquisition and education, and language learners were the least studied subject. Additionally, the Czech study topics did not diverge much from those of their international counterparts.

Meanwhile, Chen (2013) used abstracts of master's theses and PhD dissertations on second language writing (SLW) conducted at Chinese universities between 2003 and 2012 to investigate resident Chinese graduate students' research. The corpus was organized by major topic, study type, and respondents, and the results were evaluated for trends and patterns. The author found that the number of theses has increased dramatically, with a diverse range of themes being explored each year. Often, writing instruction was studied, and empirical research was the most commonly used as method. Aside from these, the author also looked into the causes for the rise in SLW studies, the wide range of subjects, the emphasis on writing education, and the high quantity of empirical studies.

Furthermore, Andresen and Zinsmeister (2018) sought to describe the stylistic contrasts between the languages of linguistics and literary studies. The research is grounded on a data-driven n-gram analysis of German PhD theses, which shows that linguistics uses metadiscourse more frequently than the other discipline.

To address a research gap in the Taiwanese language research context, Yang (2013) investigated 120 MA and PhD dissertation acknowledgments written by Taiwanese Chinese-speaking authors in terms of the generic structure and linguistic features. The findings indicate that the authors employed the same three-tier framework for writing dissertation acknowledgments. Contextual factors such as academic, socio-cultural, and geographic distinctions across the three settings, however, influenced their move building and linguistic element choices.

In the same vein, Mauludini and Kurniawan (2020) investigated the rhetorical patterns of texts, primarily in academic writing. They concentrated on the communicative goals (moves) and rhetorical methods (steps) and aimed to see if the writers' backgrounds have an impact on the rhetorical arrangement of dissertation abstracts. The study used a corpus-based approach to examine 120 humanities abstracts from four universities in England and Indonesia, and the analysis was conducted using Hyland's model. The most common patterns in both data clusters, according to the analysis, are Introduction–Purpose–Method–Product.

Content analysis was employed to conduct the abovementioned investigations. Content analysis is used in numerous domains to monitor trends and discover patterns, according to Becher and Trowler (2001), as referenced by Randolph, et al. (2012). It also allows for a deeper knowledge of the culture, language, and expectations of scholarship.

Although research movements in articles and theses have been scrutinized by

researchers worldwide, in the Philippines, very few research are published on the content analysis of language theses and dissertations. In the realm of language instruction, systematic reviews of content analyses of theses and dissertations are uncommon. There are also scant studies on the probable areas to explore in dissertation language education. Systematic reviews of content analyses of theses and dissertations are quite rare in the field of language education. Consequently, there are relatively few studies on the potential areas for theses and dissertation in language education.

Among the few studies authored by Filipinos is the research of Dayag and Dita (2012). They surveyed papers from 2000 to 2009 published in the *Philippine Journal of Linguistics*. The articles were divided into grammatical and phonological studies, language education, sociolinguistics, discourse analysis, bilingualism and code-switching, second language acquisition, as well as specific concerns and themes. The study highlights the diverse range of topics investigated and published by researchers, the majority of whom are Filipino academics. It also underscores the articles' focus on applied linguistics themes and problems.

Meanwhile, two local studies on language research content analysis were seen. Using the Create-A-Research-Space (CARS) model, Porras and Ingilan (2017) determined the occurrence and consistency of motions and steps of research introductions in *Linguistics*. The data demonstrated that there are moves and steps in the research introductions, and the bulk of the research introductions followed the CARS model, but not in the order suggested.

In addition, Porras (2019) also used Hyland's approach to investigate the presence of moves and the general structure of 30 Teacher Education student acknowledgments. The research found that the undergraduate acknowledgment structure consisted of the Thanking Move, which was the most common, followed by the Reflecting Move. Despite the absence of the Announcing Move, one distinct move, Thanking God, looked to be dominating the corpus.

Given the aforesaid premises, this research endeavors to look into published studies that looked at language theses and dissertations and identify their characteristics. It aims to offer an overview of language research content analysis and contribute to the body of knowledge on the subject, specifically in the Philippine Context. Furthermore, it may pave the way for future content analysis studies in language instruction.

This study intends to find the characteristics of research that focus on the content analysis of language theses and dissertations. Specifically, it seeks answers to these problems: What are the features of the studies reviewed in terms of thematic focus, research design, data analysis procedures, and research outputs; and, what possible areas/topics may be explored by future language researches.

Methodology

Method and Design

The systematic literature review strategy was used in this investigation. A systematic literature review (also known as a systematic review) is a method of locating, analyzing and interpreting all relevant research on a specific problem, thematic focus, or area of concentration. The specific research that form a systematic review are termed primary studies; a systematic review is a form of secondary investigation (Brereton et al., 2007).

Okoli and Schabram (2010) also recommend this strategy. They differentiate a stand-alone literature review (systematic literature review) from the other two kinds of literature review for theoretical underpinnings for primary research and graduate student theses. In its best form, a stand-alone literature review becomes a widely recognized piece of work that scholars seek out as an initial clear description of the literature when conducting research. These stand-alone assessments abridge existing findings, highlight research needs, and give a background for directing future research efforts.

Furthermore, a literature review is beneficial in a variety of ways. It allows researchers to learn about the findings of comparable or related studies, and permits them to absorb the ideas of others interested in a particular study subject, via major research findings and theories. Researchers can also use literature reviews to identify areas where more research is needed, called by Fraenkel, Wallen & Hyun (2012) as "gaps". As a result, the method was used in this endeavor.

Meanwhile, the data were gathered using document analysis techniques, with published studies on content analysis of language theses and dissertations serving as the primary source of information. The data were subjected to content analysis, and codes were employed. According to the study's parameters, these were categorized into themes.

For Neuendorf (2016), content analysis is one of the most important methodologies in educational research. Weber (1990) defines this as a technique that utilizes a series of steps to produce reliable inferences from text (Sandorova, 2019). It is further described as a tool for identifying the presence of words, themes, or concepts in qualitative data (i.e. text). The presence, meanings, and linkages of specific words, themes, or concepts can be measured and analyzed by researchers. For instance, academics can look for prejudice or partiality in the wording used in a news item. Researchers can then infer data about the text, the author(s), the readers, and even the culture and period in which the text was formed ("Content analysis, n.d.").

Cohen et al. (2007) back up the claims made above. Content analysis is a methodical set of procedures for rigorous scrutiny, inspection, and corroboration of the contents of written data. A huge quantity of data is condensed to lesser groupings of material in content analysis, or, big texts with many words are compacted by smaller or

shorter terms (Weber, 1990 cited by Sandorova, 2019).

Furthermore, Cohen et al. (2007) describe content analysis as a four-step procedure that involves coding, categorizing, comparing, and concluding. However, these phases cover key aspects of the entire content analysis process, which can be broken down into multiple sections.

Data for content analysis can come from a variety of places, including written, oral, and visual sources. Interviews, unrestricted inquiries, field study notes, interchanges, or any incidence of communicative language could be used as databases. In a study, diverse kinds of text may be scrutinized. The text must be categorized into code categories for analysis (i.e. "codes") before it can be content analyzed. After this, the codes can still be grouped into "code categories" for further data summary (Luo, 2019).

This method can also be used to quantify the incidence of specific words, phrases, subjects, or concepts in a group of historical or contemporary writings, according to Luo (2019). This means that it is used by scholars to study the goals, messages, and influences of communication content. They can also conclude about the writers and addressees of the resources they study.

In this study, the data were extracted from the published articles previously identified using predetermined standards. After the extraction of data, these were coded and categorized according to the constraints of the present study. After, the results were analyzed and interpreted.

Corpus and Corpus Selection Criteria

The initial step in meeting the goals of this study was to search several databases for every study on content analysis of language theses and dissertations. The search was conducted using eligibility criteria defined before the commencement of the identification, search, and retrieval of the published research needed to address the challenge of evidence-based practice. Though the qualifying criteria were subject to prospective revisions as the systematic review advanced through the early stages of the procedure, several of the criteria were critical to obtaining a thorough and defensible set of data (Meline, 2006). The criteria for the studies serve as an operational characterization of the problem (Abrami et al., 1988), as well as a clear guide for the research standards that will be utilized to choose which papers will be included in the review. The inclusion criteria were applied liberally at first to ensure that relevant research was included, and no study was rejected without careful consideration. Studies were initially only disqualified if they met one or more of the exclusion criteria.

The inclusion criteria were not excessively broad or too severe, based on a critical assessment strategy that tries to include works that meet some high methodological threshold of quality (Slavins, 1987 referenced by Meline, 2006). According to Lam and Kennedy (2005), if the inclusion criteria are too broad, research of poor quality may be

included, decreasing confidence in the conclusion. If the criteria are excessively stringent, the conclusions will be based on less research and may not be generalizable. As a result, the researcher defined the exact inclusion and exclusion criteria while extracting the available data from the databases.

Databases accessed included Google Scholar, EBSCO, and Proquest, among others. The keywords "content analysis", "genre analysis", "research review", "language research", "theses and dissertations", and "English language education" were used in the literature search. The search performed weekly from February 20, 2022, to April 9, 2022, yielded a total of eighty-six (86) studies.

To further select the materials to be used in this study, the following exclusion and inclusion criteria were utilized:

Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria utilized

Parameters	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Type of research	Primary research articles or scientific papers (full articles) published in peer-reviewed journals	Book reviews, opinion pieces , literary reviews, policy documents, conference proceedings
Focus	Research articles dealing with content analysis of theses and dissertations on English language, English language education, or English language research	Research articles that did not deal with content analysis of theses and dissertations on English language, English language education, or English language research
Language	Research articles or scientific papers that made use of English as a medium of writing	Research articles or scientific papers that did not make use of English as a medium of writing
DataBase	Google Scholar, EBSCO, Proquest, and other online databases accessible to the researcher	Online databases not accessible to the researcher
Time Frame	Research articles or scientific papers on content analysis of English language research published from 2016 to 2021	Research articles or scientific papers published before 2016, or after 2021

Articles from valid publications or those that have undergone a peer-review procedure are the major considerations in the selection of articles for inclusion in the criterion. Publications are essential in the discussion with other scientists regarding the methodology and significance of research projects (Powell et al., 2007).

Upon confirmation that the articles met the above-mentioned conditions, the quality of the papers was further assessed to choose the final papers for inclusion in the

analysis. The criteria for assessing a scientific paper were considered at this stage. The articles should follow the standard scientific paper structure of introduction, methods, results/findings, and conclusions and discussion (Sharp, 2002).

After a thorough evaluation of the accumulated materials, and after applying the parameters set in the criteria above, the number of studies to be reviewed was trimmed down to twenty-five (25). These met the research type, research focus, publication language, database, and time frame requirements.

Table 2: List of researches included in the systematic review

Author/s	Title	Year
1. Akbas, R.	A systematic review of the ESP (English for Specific Purposes)-based post-graduate research in Turkey	2021
2. AlHarbi, A.	Research trends in the Field of TEFL at Saudi universities: an analytical study for selected MA theses and Ph.D. Dissertations.	2019
3. Alotaibi, H.	Metadiscourse in dissertation acknowledgments: Exploration of gender differences in EFL texts.	2018
4. Atmaca, C.	Comparison of hedges in M.A. theses and PH.D. dissertations in ELT.	2016
5. Bailey, A. & Corrales, A.	Insight into Novice Research: A Critical Review of ELT Master's Theses.	2020
6. Doğan, F. Yağız, O. & Kaçar, I.	An investigation of the citation transformation types in M.A. and PhD theses.	2018
7. Ebadi, S., Salman, A. , Nguyen, T. , & Weisi, H.	Rhetorical Structure Variations in Abstracts and Introductions of Applied Linguistics Master's Theses by Iraqi and International Students.	2019
8. Getkham, K.	Authorial stance in Thai students' doctoral dissertation.	2016
9. Gursoy, E. & Özcan, E.	Finding and minding the gaps for language education in Turkey: A content analysis on doctoral dissertations in ELT programs from 2010-2020.	2021
10. Jawad, F.	Genre analysis of MA thesis abstracts by native and (Iraqi) non-native speakers of English.	2018
11. Kemal Sinan, O.	Rhetorical analysis of the doctoral abstracts on English language teaching in Turkey.	2016
12. Koroglu, Z.	A study on metadiscursive interaction in the doctoral dissertations of the native speakers of English and the Turkish speakers of English.	2018
13. Koçyiğit, M. & Erdem, C.	A content analysis of graduate research on English preparatory programs at universities.	2018
14. Massoum, Y. &	A genre-analysis of the discussion section of	2019

Yazdanmehr, E.	Iranian and English ELT theses: A comparative study.	
15. Nguyen, L. & Pramoolsook, I.	Citations in literature review chapters of TESOL master's theses by Vietnamese postgraduates.	2016
16. Othman, A.	Genre analysis: Investigation of Saudi EFL learners' PhD dissertation acknowledgements in the field of Applied Linguistics.	2018
17. Ozmen, K., Cephe, P. & Kinik, B.	Trends in doctoral research on English language teaching in Turkey.	2016
18. Ozudogru, F.	Analysis of curriculum evaluation studies conducted in foreign language education: 2005-2016.	2018
19. Panolong, K.	Tracing trends, challenges and prospects in theses on English as a second language	2018
20. Shehzad, W. & Abbas, A.	Genre analysis of generic section headings of MPhil theses' introduction section of linguistics and literature	2016
21. Shirani, S. & Chalak, A.	A genre analysis study of Iranian EFL learners' master theses with a focus on the introduction section.	2016
22. Solmaz, O.	Educational technology research trends in Turkey: Investigating graduate theses in English language teaching.	2021
23. Tullay, R.	Exploring research areas in language education dissertation.	2019
24. Wuttisrisiriporn, N.	Comparative rhetorical organization of ELT thesis introductions composed by Thai and American students.	2017
25. Zand, M. & Meihami, H.	A rhetorical move analysis of TEFL thesis abstracts: The case of Allameh Tabataba'i University.	2016

Figure 1: Major themes of the reviewed studies

Thematic focus refers to the topic which the studies investigated. Based on the topics examined, the articles assessed were divided into four groups: Research Trends and Prospects, Research Parts and Publication Considerations, Moves and Steps Structures, and Linguistic Structures.

The first group includes the trends in English language research, the frequently researched and under-researched areas in language studies, the state of ESP-based post-graduate studies, and curriculum evaluation. Studies that looked into the trends of English language research identified the major topics, the design, the methodology used, participants of the study, context and level of the research, as well as outputs produced. Moreover, frequently studied areas that were identified include language areas development, classroom interaction analysis, teacher professional development, teaching methodology, evaluation, and English language teaching. Meanwhile, the least studied areas are assessment and testing of language skills, learner phenomenon, teacher support, and culture, social and gender issues in language.

Another major focus of the research is research parts. This is comprised of exterior and content features, citation analysis, and word count and length of parts. The term exterior and content features were used by Solmaz (2021) and refer to place of completion, research type, research focus, research design, data analysis procedure, participant groups, and sample size. Aside from these, other features examined by the articles include

statistical tools used, completion year, problem statement, recommendations, paradigms, and models. Further, citation transformation and citation deployment were also surveyed, along with word count, length of introduction parts, and the relevance of generic section heading with the text.

Move-step structures analysis was also observed to be one of the focus of the research reviewed. The analyses were done in different research parts, such as abstracts, introduction, and even in discussions, as seen in the studies. There was also a comparison of the use of move-step structures in texts written by native and non-native speakers, such as Thai, Indonesian, Iraqi Arab, and Iranian learners.

Linguistic structures were also examined in the studies reviewed. Among the focus of linguistic investigations are authorial stance, gender influence on writing acknowledgments, transition marker usage, gratitude expressions, and hedging. Further, there were comparisons of the use of linguistic features in the various parts of the research, as well as comparative investigations of linguistic features written by L1 native speakers and L2 speakers.

The aforementioned findings are comparable to the results of the studies done along the lines of content analysis of language research. Latif (2018) used public journals and unpublished MA and PhD papers to investigate changes in English language education in Egypt. Teacher training, language skills, curriculum assessment, learning methods, vocabulary, and language assessment are among the most often explored areas, according to him.

In a similar vein, Kirmizi (2012) examined patterns in MA ELT programs at five Turkish universities between 2005 and 2010. Linguistic skills like listening, speaking, and others were the most commonly discussed subjects in this study, as were teaching techniques or methods, resources or programs, and computer-assisted language learning.

Another study on Jordanian research categorized 550 titles of English-language investigations to determine research sub-disciplines and topics dealt with (Bani-Khaled, 2012). The results revealed six primary focuses, five of which are linked to ELT. They also covered student, teacher, and other people's perspectives and attitudes about ELT, as well as error analysis studies.

The findings above show that the fields of content analysis and language education are widely researched areas. Various topics have been and are being conducted in the field, and various researches have been written up in the field of language education. This shows that language researchers are well-versed and give importance to the value of language and language education.

Figure 2: Distribution of research methodology utilized by the studies

The "how" of a study is referred to as the research methodology. In this study, methodology refers to whether the studies examined used content analysis, quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-method approaches to come up with valid and reliable results that addressed the study's goals and objectives.

Of the 25 studies looked at, 18 used content analysis, four used quantitative methods, one used qualitative methods, and two used mixed methods. The articles were classified based on how they were categorized by the author, whether qualitative, quantitative, mixed-method or content analysis. In the case of some studies which used both content analysis and qualitative or quantitative methods, only one method was decided on by the researcher. This was done by identifying key terms or concepts in the study which pertain to the exact methodology utilized.

As a research method, content analysis is used in determining the presence of specific terms, themes, or ideas. It permits researchers to measure and examine the presence, meanings, and correlations of specific words, themes, or concepts (Content analysis, n. d.). When the research aims and objectives are confirmatory, quantitative research is commonly used, but qualitative research is typically used when the research aims and objectives are exploratory. By combining the best of both qualitative and quantitative approaches, the mixed-method technique aims to integrate perspectives and construct a complete picture of the topic under investigation (Jansen & Warren, 2020).

Chaiyasook and Jaroongkhongdach (2014) analyzed 194 ELT theses from 2003 to 2011 in Thailand. He determined the research aim, setting, design, data sources, data collection tools, and data analysis approach. The studies made use of a quantitative research design, mixed methods, and qualitative studies, respectively. In another study, Latif (2018)

found that most of the papers he looked at used a quantitative method.

In contrast to conclusions proposing for qualitative or mixed-method approaches (Abdel Latiff, 2018; Chaiyasook & Jaroongkhongdach, 2014), the findings of Polit and Beck (2010) and Ross, et al. (2010) revealed a demand for additional studies using qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-method research to ensure equilibrium in research procedure in language research analysis. On the one hand, quantitative study is commonly seen as more "rigorous" in the global academic community, affording greater options for publication and financing. Qualitative research, conversely, allows for a "richer," more in-depth look at specific circumstances (Polit & Beck, 2010).

Motha's (2009) assessment also revealed "hybridity" as a significant component of graduate-level research. Many of the PhD scholars whose work was evaluated used "exploratory orientations toward their study" (for example, employing ethnography to evaluate language policy) and backed up their findings with varied theoretic viewpoints. This was likewise evident in the students' approaches, with a rise in mixed-method studies.

Data Analysis Procedures

Figure 3: Distribution of data analysis procedures utilized in the studies

The 25 research articles were divided into two groups in terms of data analysis procedures: those that used content analysis without software and those that used content analysis with software. Twenty of the investigations used simply content analysis, whereas the remaining five used software analysis tools or programs in addition to content analysis. AntConc Concordance, Regex, and WordSmith Tools are among the software used.

Because of technological advancements, researchers now have new means of analyzing data and are not burdened with the use of paper-pencil format or manual work,

and data analysis is supported by software analysis tools or programs. These programs support both quantitative and qualitative research not only in data analysis but in multiple phases of the research process (Cope, 2014; Woods et al., 2016).

Dollah et al. (2017) conducted a study among 10 NVivo QSR Application users to determine the software's merits and drawbacks as a data analysis tool. The most important features of NVivo, according to the participants, were its ability to help researchers manage vast amounts of data, uncover themes quickly, and manage relationships among generated themes. However, some users pointed out a few drawbacks to using this technology for scientific data processing. Participants mentioned various disadvantages, including the time it takes to learn how to use the application, the cost of individual use, and the program's inability to understand data.

John and Johnson (2000) discovered the same results in an earlier study conducted. The benefits of using qualitative data analysis software include being relieved from manual and clerical work, speeding up the process, being able to deal with large amounts of qualitative data, increased flexibility, and enhancing the validity and auditability of qualitative research. Growing pressure on academics to focus on volume and breadth rather than depth and substance, time and energy spent learning to utilize computer packages, increased commercialism, and diversion from the core labor of analysis are just a few of the concerns.

With the fast pace of how research processes are being conducted at present, the use of software or programs may prove to be very helpful. Although it may not be reliable in terms of data interpretation, it may be very convenient and advantageous not only in data analysis but in other phases as well, such as data collection and retrieval.

Research Output/s

Out of the 25 studies reviewed, it should be noted that only one had proposed an output, which is a guideline for abstract writing.

An output is a product of a study that can take many different forms. Many descriptions of what should be the outputs of research have been proposed, but "must fit the concept of research." Books and book chapters, journal articles, conference papers, creative works, research reports, designs, patents, software, and codes are some examples of research outputs ("Research output," n.d.; "What is considered a research output?" n.d.; University College Dublin, n.d.). In addition, Panolong (2019) suggests that research may provide interventions, the effectiveness of methodologies, policy comments, and other knowledge goods as a kind of output that can help policymakers with curriculum building and planning.

The possibility of gaining some advantage from research serves as a guiding concept in the conduct of inquiries or studies. Research, according to the Excellence in Research for Australia (ERA), is "the development of novel concept and/or the usage of

current information in a new and imaginative way to create new concepts, approaches, inventions, and understandings" (What is considered a research output? n. d.). This highlights the need to have a product or output, as a way of developing something new or using what is existing in a new manner, hence, paving the opportunity to "document the impact of the research" ("BeckerGuides: Research impact: Outputs and activities," 2022).

The contentions above are strongly backed by Iphofen (2011) who claimed: "If there were no research outputs, and so no other potential consequences for subjects' lives, there would be little point in conducting the research in the first place."

Possible Areas of Research

Figure 4: Possible areas of future language research

The second problem is on the possible areas that may be explored in future research. The areas were grouped into two – Pedagogy and Potentials.

Under pedagogy, researchers may want to consider language teaching (teaching approaches and methodologies, teaching of language concepts, identification of language difficulties), research teaching (teaching how to write the different sections of research, using/teaching linguistic structures to improve research writing skills), or materials development (compilation of textbooks, creation/production of new creative forms of course materials in research) as possible topics under instruction.

Along the lines of curriculum and assessment, the integration of linguistic structures and/or research writing into various writing courses (multidisciplinary integration), the utilization of results to contribute and improve pedagogical practices in various disciplines or writing courses (course enhancement), focus on testing and evaluation theory and practice (assessment), and the utilization of results in policymaking and syllabus design are possible areas of consideration.

Meanwhile, future investigations may also consider exploring other language sub-disciplines and topics such as language features, discourse analysis, comparative and

contrastive analysis, and complimentary and replication studies. Research features, such as levels and contexts, methodology, theoretical and conceptual frameworks, tools, corpus, and participants may also be further explored. Furthermore, researchers may also look into possibilities of publishing in existing databases. Proper authorities are also encouraged to look into the possible creation of research databases in their settings.

The rather large number of recommended areas for possible research implies opportunities in the field of education and research. For Tullay (2019), this opens opportunities for researchers and teachers to examine what is yet to be done and to discover untapped studies that are significant and essential in language teaching and learning. This means then that there are still many areas in the field of language research and language in general, that need to be examined and explored.

Conclusion

This study reviewed studies that looked into language thesis and dissertation analyses. The findings reveal that the corpus varies in terms of focus, ranging from research trends and features to discourse analysis, and leans toward content analysis as a research methodology and as an analysis procedure at the same time. Recommended topics for further research are in the areas of instruction, curriculum and assessment, research features, and research publication.

Notably, the quantity of research that has undergone content and genre analysis reveals that numerous studies are being conducted, written, and published in the field of language. However, as observed, the focus of the researchers should not only be limited to their discipline but should be broadened to incorporate a multi-disciplinary or interdisciplinary approach. In addition, a wide range of subjects should also be looked into, including social, cultural, and/or gender issues concerning language and language issues.

Curriculum or syllabus designers may want to use different language courses to expose learners to the fundamentals of research. Academic writing courses may be used as an avenue for integrating or even teaching the fundamentals of research to students. Results of various researches may be used both as a basis and as a material to address the weaknesses of learners in research writing.

To provide a viable solution to various concerns and issues in language education, research should achieve a balance of methods, concentrating not only on one methodology. Although content analysis may be the most viable method in the conduct of language research analyses, the variety of methods may strengthen the baseline of knowledge in the field of language research content analysis.

Furthermore, the use of data analysis software or programs may be explored by language researchers. Aside from the ease it offers, language research should also be able to cope with the rapid pace of technological advancement.

Lastly, researchers should also look into possible outputs for them to disseminate

their research findings. Aside from research publication and presentation, other forms of outputs that are beneficial to the field of language pedagogy may be produced and introduced to the language learning community.

Recommendations

The corpus of data, analysis of language theses and dissertations are diverse in terms of scope and parameters. In this study, however, only the thematic focus, methodology, data analysis procedures, and outputs were explored. Other features of the corpus may be examined, such as statistical tools, data gathering instruments, and theoretical or conceptual frameworks, among others. The linguistic and rhetorical aspects may also be considered, as well as technical aspects of the corpus.

Further, only studies published from 2016 to 2021 were included in the study. Future researchers may consider including those that were published before and after the time frame. Since only 25 studies were reviewed, and majority come from the Asian region, to attain generalizability, it is suggested that researchers increase the number of the corpus, as well as have samples from various regions of the world.

The use of data analysis software or program may also be contemplated by future researchers in analyzing their data, in addition to content analysis. The use of mixed methods may also be taken into consideration.

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